

T.C.
BAHCESEHIR UNIVERSITY
GRADUATE SCHOOL
COMMUNICATION DESIGN HEAD OF THE DEPARTMENT

THE IMPACT OF GAME BALANCE IN SERIOUS GAMES

MASTER'S THESIS

UTKU FİŐEK

ISTANBUL 2024

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ABSTRACT
THE IMPACT OF GAME BALANCE IN SERIOUS GAMES

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Games have become prominent mediums of the twenty-first century, and serious games have grown with the popularity of games. The studies about serious games generally focus on the success of serious games, but their success can only be improved by examining the game mechanics. Game balance is about why and how much a game designer should change the quantities of game mechanics. Game balance is a notably debated topic between players and game designers, but game balance in serious games is overlooked. This study investigates the effects of game balance on the non-entertainment goals of serious games.

Two serious games are selected, namely The Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism. The games are analyzed to discover how balanced they are. Then, we conducted a playtest session with participants and a survey to measure the influence of the games. The Perceived Persuasiveness Scale is used to determine the influence of the games because the selected games aim to persuade the players. Even though one of the games is more balanced, the Perceived Persuasiveness scores of the two games are similar. The results indicate that the game balance does not impact the success of a serious game.

Key Words: Game Balance, Serious Game, Perceived Persuasiveness, Game Design, Digital Game

ÖZ

CİDDİ OYUNLARDA OYUN DENGESİNİN ETKİLERİ

Utku, Fişek

Oyun Tasarımı Yüksek Lisans Programı

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Oyunların yirmi birinci yüzyılın başta gelen iletişim ortamı olmasıyla birlikte, ciddi oyunlar da popülerleşmeye başladı. Bilimsel çalışmalar çoğunlukla ciddi oyunların başarısına odaklanmasına rağmen, daha iyi ciddi oyunların nasıl geliştirilebileceği daha az çalışılmıştır. Ciddi oyunların başarısını arttırmak için oyun mekaniklerini incelemek büyük önem taşır. Oyun dengesi, oyun mekaniklerinde yapılacak nicel değişikliklerin neden ve ne kadar yapılacağını konu edinir. Oyun dengesi oyuncular ve oyun tasarımcıları arasında tartışılmasına rağmen, ciddi oyunların dengesi az çalışılmıştır. Bu çalışmanın amacı oyun dengesinin ciddi oyunların eğlence dışı amaçlarına etkisini incelemektir.

The Fiscal Ship ve *Half-Earth Socialism* isimli ikna etmeyi amaçlayan iki ciddi oyun seçildi ve ne kadar dengeli oldukları analiz edildi. Katılımcılara iki oyun oynatıldıktan sonra *Perceived Persuasiveness* ölçeği oyunların ikna ediciliğini ölçmek için uygulandı. Oyunlardan biri daha dengeli olmasına rağmen iki oyunun da ikna ediciliği benzer bir seviyede ölçüldü. Ulaşılan sonuçlar oyun dengesinin ciddi oyunların başarısını etkilemediğini göstermiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Oyun Dengesi, Ciddi Oyun, Algılanan İnanırcılık, Oyun Tasarımı, Dijital Oyunlar

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

PVP	Player vs Player
PVE	Player vs Environment
LOL	League of Legends
MTG	Magic: The Gathering
PPS	Perceived Persuasiveness Scale
AI	Artificial Intelligence
SES	Socio-Economic Status
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Statement of The Problem

Even though play comes before culture (Huizinga, 2014), play has become part of intellectual discussion in the last century. Information technologies also emerged in the last century and caused significant changes in the world. One of these changes is the rise of digital games. Today, digital games have become one of the most consumed media (Zackariasson & Wilson, 2012). Games are developed for entertainment, and players' primary motivation for playing a game is having fun (Entertainment Software Association, 2023). However, games can be utilized for other purposes; these games are called serious games.

Games research accelerated with the success of the game industry. Game research can be explored with the schema of Rules, Play, and Culture. Rules is the organization of the designed system, Play is the human experience of that system, and Culture is the larger context engaged with the system (Salen & Zimmerman, 2003). At first glance, game balance fits into Rules because of the mathematical nature of the game balance. However, human reaction to the game changes the significance of the game elements. Community reactions to a new patch are examined through Culture. A game designer has the power to control Rules, and they can influence the players with the Rules, so this thesis focuses on game balance from the lenses of Rules and Play.

The purpose of a design object shapes the design. Bags are a good example. If a bag is for laptops, the bag is carried at the back and has a rectangular shape. If a bag is for tourist travel, it is carried in the front and much smaller; on the contrary, if the bag is for mountaineering, it is as large as a young adult. Games are similar. The majority of games are for entertainment, but serious games have different purposes. Even though general design knowledge can benefit serious games, studying game design for serious games is valuable.

1.2 Purpose of The Study

The popularity of serious games increased with the growth of digital games. Even though a consensus about its definition has not been reached, nearly all developers and researchers settled that serious games are games created with the intention to entertain and to achieve at least one additional goal (Dörner, Göbel, & Effelsberg, 2016; Wattanasoontorn, Boada, García, & Sbert, 2013). Serious games are used in fields such as military, government, education, corporate, healthcare, political, religion, and art (Michael & Chen, 2006).

Mechanics are one of the core concepts of games and, therefore, serious games. Mechanics are rules and procedures that define what players should do, what the players can do, and the game's reaction (Schell, 2020). The game mechanics should be in harmony with each other, and this harmony can be produced by game balance. Brathwaite and Schreiber (2009) state that "A game is called balanced if the choices are weighted so that there is no single best method that always wins." There are seven aspects of game balance: mathematical balance, balanced difficulty, balanced progression, balanced initial condition, balance between multiple strategies, balance between game objects, and balance as fairness (Schreiber & Romero, 2022). The importance of the aspects can vary based on the type of the game.

In this research, we aim to explore the effects of game balance on additional goals of serious games. To reach this aim, we first analyze two serious games to determine their balance; then, we measure the effect of the selected serious games. The goal of the selected games is to persuade players, so we will use the Perceived Persuasiveness Scale (PPS) (Thomas, Masthoff, & Oren, 2019) to measure its persuasiveness. Finally, we compare the performance of the game balance and the result of the measurements.

1.3 Research Questions

In order to examine the effects of game balance on serious games, we seek to answer the research questions, such as

1. Does game balance affect the additional goal of serious games?

2. How does game balance affect the different aspects of persuasive goals, such as effectiveness, quality, and capability?
3. Are demographic groups affected by serious games differently?

1.4 The Significance of The Study

The success of serious games can be improved by user-based design, multi-sensory interaction, stimulation of social well-being, adaptive game design, design based on sensory data, and the standardization of evaluation (Laamarti, Eid, & El Saddik, 2014). Even though game balance is considered crucial for the success of a game (Andrade, Ramalho, Gomes, & Corruble, 2021), the investigation of game balance for the success of serious games was lacking in the literature (Becker & Görlich, 2020). This thesis intends to extend the knowledge of game balance in serious games. Professionals can use the findings of this thesis to develop finer serious games, and researchers can develop a better understanding of serious games. The secondary beneficiaries of this thesis are the players of serious games.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Serious Games

Serious games become a popular topic in academia at the start of the twenty-first century (Figure 1). Games are developed with entertainment intentions. Serious games are also raised on this entertainment value, but serious games are developed with intentions other than entertainment (Ute, Michael, & Peter, 2009). The definition of serious games is “a digital game created with the intention to entertain and to achieve at least one additional goal” (Dörner et al., 2016, p. 3). Other studies include all types of games instead of just digital games (Wattanasoontorn et al., 2013). Including non-digital games in serious games may result in a better definition because board games like Monopoly are designed for purposes other than entertainment (Pilon, 2015).

Figure 1. Number of serious games (Laamarti et al., 2014).

Serious games may have various goals, such as teaching, training, changing the behavior, changing the attitude and changing the knowledge (Giunti et al., 2015). The domain in which the serious game is also an essential factor that may change its design. The major domains in which serious games are commonly developed are military, government, education, corporate, healthcare, politics, religion, and art (Michael &

Chen, 2006). Each domain has more specific aims for serious games. For example, in healthcare, serious games are used for prevention, assessment, diagnosis, rehabilitation, and patient education (McCallum & Boletsis, 2013).

Serious games have numerous advantages. According to (Dörner et al., 2016), These advantages are being a fun experience, increasing user motivation, reaching users on an emotional level, higher goal achievement, having immediate feedback, being adaptive, and being an intelligent tool. Papastergiou (2009) extends the advantages by adding its engaging nature and the social learning environment it provides. The learning environment can support multi-sensory, active, experiential, and problem-based learning. In this environment, players can use their previous knowledge to proceed, rapidly test their ideas, and evaluate themselves with a scoring system.

2.2 Game Balance

The second section of the literature review will examine the concept of game balance. Resources from the practitioners and the scientific community will be used to explain the concept. First, this section will discuss the definition of game balance. Then, it will explore the recurring concepts of game balance. Furthermore, it will present the methods, techniques, and tools used for achieving game balance. Finally, it will explore the recent discussions about game balance.

2.2.1 What is game balance. Authors attempted to define game balance, but they have yet to reach a consensus. According to Adams and Rollings (2003), game balance is hard to define because of the player factor. Sirlin (2009: p.1). defines game balance for multi-player games as “A multiplayer game is balanced if a reasonably large number of options available to the player are viable--especially, but not limited to, during high-level play by expert players” His definition does not cover single-player games. Adams (2010) took another approach; instead of defining game balance, he defined balanced game and game balancing. He proposes that fair, medium-difficulty, and skill-based games are balanced, and game balancing is a designing and tuning process to achieve a balanced game. He is one of the first authors to list the

attributes of game balance. Difficulty adjustment is predominantly appropriate for PvE games because, in PvP games, other players determine the difficulty.

As stated by Sylvester (2013), game balance is adjusting game mechanics to regulate the relative strength of different characters, strategies, units, teams, or tools. Wang (2023) states the aim of game balance is to design equally viable options. Schell (2020: 212) also takes on a similar approach; he states, “Balancing a game is nothing more than adjusting the elements of the game until they deliver the experience you want”. Schell (2020) emphasizes that the goal of game balance is to deliver the experience the designer wants to accomplish. Even though this is the most comprehensive definition, it may change with various contexts, in addition to that the practitioners and academics perceive game balance differently in these contexts.

Schreiber and Romero (2022) list the contexts where the game balance is perceived differently. The first one is the mathematical balance, which is about the numeric relations of game elements. The second one is balancing the difficulty, also known as a difficulty curve. The third one is balanced progression, which is the rate at which the players go through the duration of the game, such as power, gameplay, difficulty, and narrative. The fourth one is the balanced initial conditions. The initial conditions are balanced if all players have a similar opportunity to win the game. The fifth one is the balance between multiple strategies. PvP games generally provide multiple strategies to win the game. These strategies ought to be equally viable in balanced games. The sixth one is the balance between game elements; this kind of balance exists when the game elements have different features that enables them to be preferred in different situations. The last one is balance as fairness. Fairness is related to many concepts. For example, difficulty spikes disrupt fairness, and being unable to control the game's outcome makes the player feel that the game is unfair.

2.2.2 Core concepts of game balance

2.2.2.1 Fairness. Even though players have diverse concepts of fairness, games need to be perceived as fair to be enjoyable. If a player makes an unknowing decision earlier in the game that will affect the win chance and if the player finds out that the decision actually determined the end result, the game will be perceived as unfair.

Another example of unfairness is killing the player's avatar when the player does not have the option to prevent it. Protecting new players in a multi-player PvP game from experienced players may be considered fair (Adams & Rollings, 2003).

Players expect different qualities from fair PvE and PvP games. One of the qualities of a fair PvE game is having a consistently challenging difficulty level. These challenges should be similar to the games in the same genre. Being stuck in a position without any option to escape may undermine the perception of fairness. Fair PvE games predominantly provide enough information before the player makes an essential decision. In fair PvP games, players start the game with an equal chance to win and any advantage acquired by a player can be prevented or influenced by another player (Adams, 2010). Sirlin (2009) focuses on PvP games and emphasizes having equal chances at the start of the game. Game elements may have niche uses or need specific conditions to be used during the game, but elements chosen at the start of the game should be viable. For example, a unit in a strategy game may be weak against an enemy unit while being strong against another one. A faction in a strategy game should have an equal chance to win against all enemy factions.

2.2.2.2 Relationships of game elements. Game elements are in-game entities such as buildings, weapons, units, heroes, and spells. Adams and Rollings (2003) define two types of relations: Transitive and intransitive. Transitive relations are linear one-way relationships of multiple game elements. Transitive relationships can be formulated as A beats B, B beats C, and C does not beat any other game elements. Even though transitive relationships appear impractical, they can be useful in games with an endpoint. For example, in a first-person shooter game, players may start with a weak pistol. After reaching a certain level, the player receives a shotgun that dispatches enemy units more conveniently. Transitive relationships motivate the player to proceed forward towards a target. In X-COM 2, warden armor is more potent than predator armor, and predator armor is more powerful than kevlar armor. The logical choice for the player is to use warden armor, but warden armor requires research, which is only available at a certain point in the game. This transitive relationship motivates the players to play so that they can have the better armor (Firaxis Games, 2016).

Figure 2. Transitive relationship.

Intransitive relationships can be formulated as A beats B, B beats C, and C beats A. Its textbook example is rock, paper, scissors. If the game elements have the same winning probability, the decision-making will become less interesting. The condition of game elements' effectiveness may vary in the gameplay to make decision-making more interesting. For example, A and B are two units that can operate in the air and submerged under the water. If A beats B underwater and B beats A in the air, the decision-making will be more interesting (Adams & Rollings, 2003). Intransitive relationships are also called circular balance or cyclical balance. Schell (2020) claims that intransitive relationships are suitable for achieving fairness. Intransitive relationships also assist in creating an engaging and interesting metagame environment (Portnow, 2012). Sirlin (2009) enhances intransitive relationships with Yomi Layers. Yomi means “reading” in Japanese as reading the opponent’s mind. Let’s assume there are two players: player 1 and player 2. At layer 1, player 2 executes a move to counter player 1’s move. At layer 2, player 1 executes a move to counter player 2’s counter move. At layer 3, player 2 executes a counter move to counter player 1’s counter move. Generally, the move at layer 4 is the original move of player 1.

Figure 3. Intransitive relationship.

2.2.2.3 Feedback. A feedback loop emerges when the effects of a change in an element of a system come back and affect the same element. Negative feedback loops maintain a balance in the system. For instance, in Civilization, as the player's city grows, the population requires more food. This leads to a stable city population. Negative feedback makes the system more resilient to change. A positive feedback loop empowers its cause. For instance, a microphone picks up a sound, and a speaker reproduces the sound louder. The microphone picks up the sound again, and the speaker reproduces it even louder. Chess is an instructive example. If a player captures an opponent's piece, it will become easy to capture a new piece. Positive feedback can be used to create an arms race in PvP games, but it may also cause a deadlock if the elements depend exclusively on each other. In StarCraft, players need a mining unit to harvest more mines and mines to produce a mining unit. If a player is out of the mining unit and mine, the game will be over for the player (Adams & Dormans, 2012).

Positive feedback makes the winning player more likely to win. Finishing the game in a timely manner is beneficial, but the losing player should have an opportunity to win. There are several ways to neutralize the adverse effects of positive feedback. A negative feedback or chance factor can be used (Adams, 2010; Adams & Rollings, 2003). The effects of the positive feedback can be delayed to give the losing players a chance to act (Adams & Rollings, 2003). Deep gameplay may emerge if positive

feedback is unrelated to the winning condition. The difficulty of single-player games can be increased to match the exponential effect of positive feedback. In PvP games, allowing players to group up against the player in the lead preserves the winning chance of the losing players (Adams, 2010).

2.2.2.4 Difficulty. The combined effect of exerted physical effort and experienced mental workload defines the difficulty of play (Hsu, Wen, & Wu, 2007). Csikszentmihalyi (1990) proposes the concept of flow. If the challenge is too easy, people will be bored, and if the challenge is too difficult, people will get anxious. The middle path is the state of flow, which is productive and enjoyable. State of flow also applies to game difficulty (Adams, 2010).

Adams (2010) argues that the difficulty players experience is more influential than mathematical difficulty. He defines absolute difficulty as the amount of required skill to overcome the challenge, including time pressure. The absolute difficulty is convenient to compare levels. The relative difficulty is the absolute difficulty compared to the power provided to the player. As the game provides more power to the player, the relative difficulty decreases. The perceived difficulty is the difficulty the player feels. Providing more powers to the player and the gain of experience, makes the player perceive the game easier. The perceived difficulty should arise or remain flat. To manage difficulty progression, the game designer should increase the absolute difficulty while giving the player new powers to keep the player motivated, but only some games are suitable for giving players more power. Being aware of the experience gained by the player is necessary to control difficulty progression. Playtesting allows designers to identify dips and spikes. Players' experience increases while playing and decreases while not playing. Players usually take a break at the end of the level, so the difficulty level should increase during the level and decrease at the start of the new level. The player's native talent and previous experience are out of the designer's control, but giving a chance to select the difficulty level may be a solution. If difficulty mode is available, it is the first game balance element that the player perceives (Adams & Rollings, 2003). Game modes unlocked after the game is completed, such as ascension levels of *Slay the Spire*, can also be considered difficulty modes (Giovannetti, 2019).

Figure 4. Absolute, relative, and perceived levels of difficulty (Adams, 2010).

2.2.2.5 Dominant strategy and meaningful choices. A dominant strategy, a game theory term, is a strategy that never loses. If a strategy always wins, we call it a strongly dominant strategy. A dominant strategy is less concrete in game design because most games are continuous, and changing player behaviors and capabilities can affect the game's outcome. Envisioning an ideal player may help to develop mathematically balanced games, but actual players are humans, and these games could end up not being fun (Adams & Rollings, 2003).

Meaningful choices are choices that are viable and cause different outcomes from other choices (Sirlin, 2009). In a thought experiment, Felder (2015) assumes a card wins the game without any limitation called All Too Easy (dominant strategy). All Too Easy eradicates meaningful choices; thus, it ruins an exciting gameplay environment. Exactly equal options also eradicate meaningful choices because if all the choices result in the same outcome, the choice is inconsequential. Perfectly balanced games can be useful if the game does not prioritize strategic gameplay. A successful strategy game should have multiple viable strategies. Some strategies can be better than others, and the game can still be balanced if each strategy has a weakness to be exploited.

Balanced games should provide meaningful choices (Adams, 2010), and gameplay is primarily about deciding what to do, and poor balance limits meaningful choices. That is where the importance of game balance comes from. Poor game balance gives birth to dominant strategies, which makes the other strategies useless. Players may still use the other strategies for different reasons, like to have fun or a handicap, but this does not reduce the severity of the dominant strategy (Burgun, 2011). Sirlin (2009) stressed that the designer should primarily eliminate dominant strategies.

2.2.2.6 Symmetrical & asymmetrical design. A game is symmetrical if the starting conditions are equal and these games are mostly balanced, but they are also more prone to become dull and can be perceived as artificial (Adams, 2010). Functional symmetry is when the starting conditions are not precisely the same, but the functions of starting abilities, skills, units, and so forth are the same. For example, in Red Alert 2, each faction has one basic tank, one anti-air tank, one carrier, and one special tank, but they are all different (Adams & Rollings, 2003). Successful games are symmetrical, but even symmetrical games need to be balanced in terms of elements of the same side (Burgun, 2011). Symmetric games are the easiest to balance, while asymmetric games are more complicated to balance because of the different starting conditions (Wang, 2023). Symmetric and asymmetric games can be considered as a scale instead of a category (Sirlin, 2009).

2.2.2.7 Chance and probability. Chance is not a quantitative but a relative description; it is used when numbers are not available. The qualitative description is probability, which is a number between 0 and 1. A probability of 1 means it will definitely happen, and 0 means it will not happen (Schreiber & Romero, 2022).

The chance factor is used in many games for numerous reasons. A game is called solvable if the entire play space can be calculated. Chance and randomness prevent or delay the game from becoming solvable. Pure strategy games often result in favor of a better player. These kinds of games can be frustrating for less skillful players. Chance gives a possibility to win for less skillful players, and bad luck can be a scapegoat. The games without random factors always start precisely the same, and fixed patterns often emerge, such as chess openings. Chance and random elements in games can expand the variations, so it increases the replayability of the games. When

a crucial point in the game is determined by chance, players get excited to see the results. Chance can be more engaging even for pure strategy game players because calculating the probability increases the depth of the game (Schreiber & Romero, 2022). Even though chance can be beneficial, it is essential to balance it with players' skills, and chance should not surpass skill. These suggestions can be used to prevent chance from becoming dominant: using the chance seldom, using it frequently but with low impact, informing the player about the likelihood of the outcomes to choose what to do, and allowing the player how much to risk (Adams, 2010).

2.2.3 Methods, techniques, and tools for balancing. Researchers and practitioners developed several methods, tools, and techniques to balance games more profoundly. These means span from general, as in setting a core rule, to specific, as in changing a parameter.

The most general method is to design the core rules of the game and to design the rest based on them. Core rules simplify the tweaking process and clarify the programming (Adams & Rollings, 2003). Having core rules (Philosophy) is also valuable for game companies. Core rules do a service to resolve intricate problems. It helps to keep employees on the same track. Even former and current employees can be on the same page through core rules (Street, 2017). For example, the Core rule (The balance goal) of Slay the Spire is “Every card should have a place” (Giovannetti, 2019).

A diverse population usually plays games. This raises the problem of balancing for players with diverse skill levels. A game can be balanced for high-level players, but it does not mean it is balanced for ordinary players (Burgun, 2011). The former executive producer of Riot Games, Greg Street, pointed out that high-level players have better skills in terms of click speed, coordination, and execution. They also have better strategies than new players. A champion might have a high win rate for high-level players and a low win rate for low-level players; that is a concrete example of why balancing for players with different skill levels is difficult. LoL players with a good internet connection can play certain champions better, and different nationalities may have different preferences. That is why game designers pay attention to data from

players from distinct countries. Balancing is not always for players. Balancing for pro players is usually for viewers (Street, 2017).

Understanding the type of players is essential to balance the game for the diverse players. Hamari and Tuunanen scrutinized the marketing literature to understand the category of segmentations. Geographic segmentation divides people based on location, such as country, city, and so on. Demographic segmentation groups are in accordance with descriptive characteristics such as age, gender, or occupation. Psychological segmentation tries to categorize based on attitudes, lifestyles and values. Lastly, behavioral segmentation categorizes users according to their usage behavior of the product. A gamer can seldom play a game to relieve after a stressful workday (Hamari & Tuunanen, 2014).

Especially in intransitive relationships, game elements can be used equally and predictably. It is crucial to prevent predictability. To prevent this, game designers can use unquantifiable costs, called shadow costs. Shadow costs lead to the formation of trade-offs. The trade-off is the relation between game elements that have distinct qualifications and cannot be compared with each other. For example, pistons are better at land fighting, but harpoons are better underwater (Adams & Rollings, 2003). Game elements with trade-offs are orthogonally different. Orthogonal elements may prevent the dominant strategy from showing up (Adams, 2010). *Destiny 2* is a shooter game with PvE and PvP content; PvE content involves boss fights. In *Destiny 2*, swords are great damage dealers, but they must be used at close range so they cannot be used against melee bosses. Linear fusion rifles have long-range and high critical damage, but some bosses do not have a spot for critical damage, so they are useless against them. Anarchy is a grenade launcher in *Destiny*. It sticks a device on the enemy and deals consistent damage over time regardless of the critical damage spot, but it requires a long duration to be advantageous. Swords, however, can deal damage in a short duration (Bungie, 2017).

Games can be designed in such a way that the dominant strategies can be undermined in the gameplay. These ways are called safeguards. For example, players are allowed to determine the cost of the game elements and design every strategy with its counter strategy (Felder, 2015). Sirlin (2009) calls the same phenomena self-

balancing forces. Safeguards can solve balance problems before they emerge. In the fighting game *Guilty Gear XX*, the stuns get shorter as the enemy hits repeatedly. If there is an infinite combo, the victim will be able to block it. The longer the characters are juggled in the air, the stronger the gravity becomes. This makes infinite juggles impossible.

The game designers may need a system to evaluate the strength of the game elements, but in most genres, it is impossible. Adams and Rollings (2003) confirmed that such a method called point distribution is used in roleplaying games. They suggested that the attributes that are improved with points should be equally useful in the game and should not affect each other. Mayo (2018) illustrated a different system for card games based on the cost of the card and its power. These two parameters allow us to build a graph. The power curve is a graph where the y-axis is the power of the game element, and the x-axis is the cost of the game element. The power curve provides the means to compare games in the same genre. In *Hearthstone*, the power curve is not linear because a high-cost card is more powerful than two low-cost cards with equal combined costs. It is not linear because low-cost cards are more flexible, and high-cost cards cannot be played in the early games. *Magic: The Gathering* contains different mana types. Playing high-cost cards in *Magic: The Gathering* is more laborious because the players need to collect the correct type of mana. Low-cost cards in *Magic: The Gathering* are more flexible compared to high-cost cards because mana types are less restrictive in low-cost cards. This comparison between *Hearthstone* and *Magic: The Gathering* results in low-cost *hearthstone* cards being more powerful than *Magic: The Gathering* cards and high-cost *Magic: The Gathering* cards being more powerful than *Hearthstone* cards.

Figure 5. Power curve of Magic: The Gathering and Hearthstone (Mayo, 2018).

Creating tier lists for game elements helps to design balanced games. The tier list categorizes game elements in terms of their strength. Five tiers can be used: god tier, top tier, middle tier, bottom tier, and garbage tier. The designer should eliminate the god and garbage tiers to provide better games. Last, a game designer should recognize a strong entity that other entities can counter. If these entities are chosen at the start of the game and cannot be changed throughout the game, the designer should take care of them (Sirlin, 2009). According to Jaffe (2015), Match-up charts are better than tier lists. A match-up chart is a two-axis chart where all game elements are listed on both axes, and their intersection shows the win probability of the game element. The advantage of match-up charts is that they are well-defined. A tier does not have a concise meaning, but 60% on a match-up chart means character A is 60% more likely to win.

handicap to assess its difficulty (Rouse, 2001). Adams suggests (2010) four tweaking methods for game designers to avoid time waste. Keeping the records of the changes prevents testing the same configuration again and makes it easier to learn from the former test. Changing one parameter at a time may seem exhausting, but changing one parameter teaches the effects of that parameter. Making small adjustments may not be recognized. Doubling or halving the parameter is a good starting point to see the effect. Pseudorandom numbers are beneficial for seeing the effect of chance.

Conducting playtesting can be expensive and time-consuming. Digital tools can be used to improve the game balance further before playtesting. Browne (2008) developed Ludi, which is software for automatically evaluation and synthesizing games. It has three modules: Strategy, criticism, and synthesis. The strategy module evaluates boards and plans moves. Criticism aesthetically evaluates the game. Synthesis modifies the existing rules to produce new games. The strategy module of Ludi can be helpful in evaluating the balance of the games, but Ludi is limited to turn-based, perfect information board games. Biped is a system where game designers can produce prototypes. Biped enables human playtesting and machine play testing and allows game designers to determine game design and game balance issues (Smith, Nelson, & Mateas, 2009). Burda et al. (2019) developed an AI that can act in different environments, including 48 Atari games. Even though this AI does not use extrinsic motivation, it performs better than random agents. Although the AI does not directly give feedback about the game balance, its gameplay can be used to understand game balance flaws. Machinations is a framework that uses diagrams to represent the resource flow of a game. Simulation games, strategy games and board games can be simulated with Machinations to analyze game balance without playtests and even game build. Machinations cannot simulate spatial elements such as level design or tactical maneuverability (Dormans, 2011).

Figure 7. Machinations diagram.

Balance analysis can be done with observation. The game designer can observe the frequency of occurrence of game elements or emergent factors. Game designers can monitor the use frequency of squares and see middle squares are used more than edge squares. However, observation only occasionally delivers correct results. Knights are used more than the king, but the king is the most critical piece in chess. The game designers can measure a player's win rate who is prohibited from accessing a specific game element against a regular player. This method is called restricted play. For example, Game designers can observe the win rate of the knightless player against a regular player and the win rate of the bishopless player against a regular player. The difference between the win rates is the strength between the knight and the bishop (Jaffe, 2013).

2.2.4 Recent discussions about game balance.

2.2.4.1 Is slight imbalance better. Portnow (2012) claims that a slight imbalance in games is favorable. For example, chess is a balanced game but suffers from established fixed strategies. Players must study chess for decades to discover new tactics and strategies. Another example is the original StarCraft. When StarCraft was numerically balanced, the decisions became easy to calculate, and the game shifted from a strategy game to an action game. On the contrary, League of Legends (LoL)

has slight imbalances that produce an evolving metagame. He notes that the imbalance should be crafted carefully. The intransitive relationship of the game elements is essential to have an engaging metagame.

We Didn't Playtest This At All is a two-minute card game. The game is extremely unbalanced, but it is still fun and successful because the unfairness in the game is evident to players. The players' expectations are set so the players play the game as a short filler game or decide who will go first. *The Great Dalmuti* is also clearly an unbalanced game. In the game, a positive feedback loop keeps the winning player winning and the losing player losing. The Great Dalmuti is still fun because the players understand its unfairness and play accordingly. The game allows the losing player to climb the position step by step. The climbing creates an emerging story of an underdog, which is commonly admired (Schreiber & Romero, 2022).

Burgun (2011) advocates that the game balance is indispensable for the games. A game can be fun and unbalanced, but it is fun despite being unbalanced. He considers two reasons why a slight imbalance may seem preferable. The first one is game balance, which is a complex system and a game may seem unbalanced from one point of view, but it is balanced from a more complete point of view. The second one is that anything can be fun with the right approach, such as brushing teeth. Fun is not a concrete concept to assess games alone.

2.2.4.2 Should AI testers be used. Sirlin (2009) argues that game designers can balance games with rules only up to a point; after that point, game designers need intuition. The game balance is too complex to be solved. Intuition is the best tool to handle highly complex problems. Data from users is helpful, but designers should approach it cautiously because the data may be misleading. Riot Games hires humans to balance LoL instead of machine learning because perceived balance is more important than mathematical balance. A game designer's experience-based judgment is more suitable for interpreting perceived balance (Street, 2017).

Game production requires playtesting to assess and validate the game's most recent version. Game progression, narrative, aesthetics, player experience and player behavior can be evaluated with playtesting. Human playtesting is expensive and time-

consuming. AI playtesting may evaluate the technical components of the game so that it can reduce the cost of human playtesting (Önal, 2023). Game designers balance their game by playing it or using spreadsheets before playtesting. Early balance attempts are invaluable for balancing but are essentially flawed because they may miss the diversity of player behavior, and game designers' bias may affect the result. Games reach the playtesting phase with plentiful flaws. The number of flaws can be reducible with AI tools (Jaffe, 2013).

Chapter 3

Methodology

The methodology section introduces the research design of the study in addition to game selection, game balance analysis, setting and participants, and data collection procedures. Finally, it presents the limitations of the study.

3.1 Research Design

This study aims to examine the effects of game balance on non-entertainment goals of serious games. Mixed research methods will be used to reach this goal. Two serious games have been selected. First, they will be analyzed to evaluate their balance. Then, a playtest session with a survey will be conducted. In this survey, participants will play the abovementioned two games and fill out a questionnaire. The evaluations and the survey results will be compared to reach a conclusion.

3.2 Game Selection

At least two serious games are required to show the effects of game balance. After exploring serious games in the market, The Fiscal Ship(1st Playable Productions, 2016) and Half-Earth Socialism (Tseng, Pham, Pendergrass, & Vettese, 2022) games were selected. Games, in general, are inherently different from each other. However, the selected games had to be similar to each other to minimize the factors that can affect the goals of serious games. In both games, the player plays as a governor of a large society, and the player needs to decide which policies will pass. Both games utilize cards or card-like mechanics for decision making and charts are used to visualize essential stats. The games employ the complexity of policy-making to reach their goals. Half-Earth Socialism is about climate change. The Fiscal Ship is about fiscal policies, but the player has the freedom to choose governing goals. The “Fight Climate Change” goal will be mandatory to choose to increase the similarity between the games.

3.3 Game Balance Analysis

The Balance of a game is difficult to evaluate. Numerous tools are developed to assess game balance, but they can be used for games with specific qualifications. These tools are also flawed because they only evaluate games mathematically and almost all the time overlook the human factor. Playtesting is used to evaluate the game

balance in the gaming industry, but a rigorous scientific instrument has not yet been developed. In this research, we will evaluate game balance by analyzing the games using Jesse Schell's (2020) twelve most common types of game balance as a framework. The game balance types are developed for all games, but two games will be analyzed, so some types were irrelevant for our analysis. Each type is reviewed below to understand if they are relevant to the games in the research.

3.3.1 Fairness. Fairness in a game can be provided by symmetries in games. However, asymmetrical games have various advantageous, such as; simulating the real world, extending game space, enabling more personalized play styles, creating an opportunity to fix the skill gap between players, and creating more interesting games (Schell, 2020).

There are four questions to ask while examining fairness.

Should my game be symmetrical? Why?

Should my game be asymmetrical? Why?

Which is more important: that my game is a reliable measure of who has the most skill or that it provides an interesting challenge to all players?

If I want players of different skill levels to play together, what means will I use to make the game interesting and challenging for everyone?

3.3.2 Challenge vs. success. Matching the difficulty of the game with players' skills is desirable. Too difficult games are frustrating, and too easy games are boring. Game designers may have the urge to make games more difficult to extend play time, but the players can become frustrated by difficult games and stop playing. Increasing the difficulty with each success helps to adjust the difficulty. Designing the easy levels of the games in such a way that more experienced players can pass them quickly prevents experienced players from getting bored in easy levels. Levels can have different success layers. Letting a player pass a level with suboptimal performance keeps an inexperienced player in the game. It also allows the experienced player to play the same level with a more ambitious goal. Offering difficulty selection to the players gives them an opportunity to play the right difficulty for them. Giving bonuses to losing players can keep them engaged. The game designers should run tests with

players with varying skill levels to design the game for a broader audience (Schell, 2020).

There are six questions to ask while examining challenges.

What are the challenges in my game?

Are they too easy, too hard, or just right?

Can my challenges accommodate a wide variety of skill levels?

How does the level of challenge increase as the player succeeds?

Is there enough variety in the challenges?

What is the maximum level of challenge in my game?

3.3.3 Meaningful choices. Choices are meaningful when they have an effect on how the game proceeds. If a racing game has fifty cars, but they have the exact attributes, then it means the player does not have a choice. On the other hand, if this game has ten different cars, but one is better than the others, it again means the player does not have a choice. If one choice is superior to the other, the superior choice is called the dominant strategy. Dominant strategies hinder the games from being fun. The number of meaningful choices also needs to be considered. The player will be overwhelmed if the choices exceed the player's desires. The player will be frustrated if the choices fall behind the player's desire (Schell, 2020).

There are four questions to ask while examining meaningful choices.

What choices am I asking the player to make?

Are they meaningful? How?

Am I giving the player the right number of choices? Would more make them feel more powerful? Would less make the game clearer?

Are there any dominant strategies in my game?

3.3.4 Skill vs. chance. Chance and skill are two adverse mechanics of a game. Skill-based games are tenser, and they usually judge which player is better; on the other hand, chance-based games are more relaxed and casual. Balancing skill and

chance requires an understanding of the players. Players' age, gender, and culture may affect their preferences. Alternating the use of chance and skill is a common way to find the sweet spot. For example, a dice can determine how far a character can go, but the player decides where to go (Schell, 2020).

There are four questions to ask while examining skill vs. chance.

Are my players here to be judged (skill) or to take risks (chance)?

Skill tends to be more serious than chance: is my game serious or casual?

Are parts of my game tedious? If so, will adding elements of chance enliven them?

Do parts of my game feel too random? If so, will replacing elements of chance with elements of skill or strategy make the players feel more in control?

3.3.5 Head vs. hand. This type of balance examines the contrast between physical activity and thinking. Most games utilize head and hand together. The target market for the game is critical to understand where to place the game between head and hand. The games we will analyze in this study are head games. They do not demand physical activity other than moving the mouse without time pressure and reading texts from a screen. Since the games are on the same end of the spectrum, this type of game balance will not be included in this research (Schell, 2020).

3.3.6 Competition vs. cooperation. Competition and cooperation are evolutionary motives. Competing with other animals is part of survival. Cooperating with others is more advantageous than acting as an individual. These two motives are frequently used in games, and occasionally, both are used together. The games we will analyze are single-player games, and they do not subsume competition or cooperation, so we will not include this type of balance in this research (Schell, 2020).

3.3.7 Short vs. long. Short games may prevent players from developing meaningful strategies, and the players may avoid long games because they require a time commitment. The length of a game is predominantly affected by the win or lose conditions. For example, in the Minotaur, four players compete with each other in a maze. The players can run without confronting each other for a long duration. To prevent this, the designers of the game added a new level. After twenty minutes, all

players are teleported to a small room where no one can stay alive for long (Schell, 2020).

3.3.8 Rewards. Rewards are one of the significant reasons for playing games. Several forms of rewards can be encountered in games. Praise is the simplest form of reward. The game tells the player they are doing great through a character or a statement. The primary purpose of points is to measure players' success, but they often motivate players. Prolonged play is a form of reward because it may mean a higher score and a measurement of success. The players not only want to be evaluated as successful but also want to explore. Allowing players to reach new levels or areas is a gateway reward. An appealing sound effect or an animation can be a reward. Players are mainly inclined to express themselves. Decorations, clothes or skins satisfy the players' urge. People wish to be more powerful. Empowering the players is another way to reward players. Players can be empowered by receiving new abilities, weapons, potent pieces, and so on. The game can grant resources as a reward. Status is also a form of reward. Players can seek high leaderboard rankings, achievements, or any other form of status. Completing is the final form of reward. It gives an unusual sensation of closure, which is hard to obtain in real life. These reward forms can be combined (Schell, 2020).

Different games should give different forms of rewards in different amounts. In most cases, including more types is better. Increasing the amount of rewards through the game is preferable because players adapt to the rewards and are less affected by them if they keep receiving the same rewards. Varying the amount of rewards excites the players. Awarding ten points is less satisfying than awarding thirty points one-third of the time (Schell, 2020).

There are six questions to ask while examining rewards.

What rewards is my game giving out now? Can it give out others as well?

Are players excited when they get rewards in my game, or are they bored by them? Why?

Getting a reward you don't understand is like getting no reward at all. Do my players understand the rewards they are getting?

Are the rewards my game gives out too regular? Can they be given out in a more variable way?

How are my rewards related to one another? Is there a way that they could be better connected?

How are my rewards building? Too fast, too slow, or just right?

3.3.9 Punishment. Punishment in a game sounds controversial, but accurately used punishment can increase enjoyment. The possibility of losing resources makes the resources more valuable. This possibility enhances players' excitement by allowing them to take a risk. The possibility of loss makes success more satisfying. Punishment is also used to adjust the difficulty (Schell, 2020).

Various forms of punishment can be encountered across games. Punishment forms are mostly the opposite of reward forms. Shaming is the opposite of praise. A game can punish a player by showing texts that say "missed" or "defeated." Loss of points is a severe punishment, and even traditional games avoid it. Shortened play is the opposite of prolonged play; furthermore, game designers can enhance it by terminating the play early. Setback is a frequent form of punishment in the games that focuses on proceeding to the end. Spawning at the start of the level or the checkpoint is a common setback. Removal of power is another form of punishment that players might find unfair because they value and appreciate the power they have achieved. Removing the power temporarily is a modest way to remove power. Resource depletion is another typical form of punishment (Schell, 2020).

Reward is a better tool to motivate people than punishment. It is important to communicate to the player that the punishments have a reason and are fair because otherwise, the player would feel a lack of control. Unfair punishments can cause players to stop playing the game. Even though a handful of players enjoy punishment-heavy games such as Darksouls, they also have a limit (Schell, 2020).

There are five questions to ask while examining punishments.

What are the punishments in my game?

Why am I punishing the players? What do I hope to achieve by it?

Do my punishments seem fair to the players? Why or why not?

Is there a way to turn these punishments into rewards and get the same or a better effect?

Are my strong punishments balanced against commensurately strong rewards?

3.3.10 Freedom vs. controlled experience. Games are interactive mediums. The interactivity is achieved by giving the player control and freedom, but freedom can be tedious. Curating player control and cutting out boring and irrelevant actions enhance the gameplay (Schell, 2020).

3.3.11 Simple vs. complex. Complexity and simplicity can be perceived positively or negatively. A simple game can be elegant or dull, and a complex game can be deep or confusing. There are two types of complexity: Innate and emergent. If the rules of the game are complex, it is called innate complexity. Innate complexity is hard to learn and is mostly perceived as unfavorable. If the rules of the game are simple but the game that arises from it is complex, it is called emergent complexity. Emergent complexity is usually praised. Innate complexity is necessary when the game simulates real life (Schell, 2020).

There are four questions to ask while examining simplicity vs. complexity.

What elements of innate complexity do I have in my game?

Is there a way this innate complexity could be turned into emergent complexity?

Do elements of emergent complexity arise from my game? If not, why not?

Are there elements of my game that are too simple?

3.3.12 Detail vs. imagination. Games are structures that generate mental models in the players' minds. Games provide details, and the players imagine the rest. Adjusting the level of detail is one of the responsibilities of game designers. The details that help to understand the game mechanics will quicken learning the game. The details that inspire imagination are more valuable than the details that block imagination. When a player encounters a detailed object, the player will imagine the object in detail, even if the object is smaller and simple for the rest of the game. The players do not

need an abundance of details if they are already familiar with the situation. Poorly implemented details will interfere with players' imagination, so no details are generally better than low-quality details (Schell, 2020).

There are seven questions to ask while examining detail vs. imagination.

What must the player understand to play my game?

Can some element of imagination help them understand that better?

What high-quality, realistic details can we provide in this game?

What details would be below quality if we provided them? Can imagination fill the gap instead?

Can I give details that the imagination will be able to reuse again and again?

What details I provide inspire imagination?

What details I provide stifle imagination?

3.4 Setting and Participation

The study was conducted face-to-face and online. The location for face-to-face sessions was chosen according to the convenience of the participants. An appropriate setting was provided for the participants. All gameplay sessions were conducted in 2 weeks. Each participant was assigned an ID to preserve the confidentiality of the participants.

The participants were reached through convenience sampling. They also needed to fulfill additional criteria to be included in the study. The first criteria was to be familiar with digital games. The participants who have played five digital games in the last three years were considered familiar with computer games. Additionally, the participants needed to play the examined games for the first time during the gameplay session. Fifteen participants were recruited. One participant is removed from the research, because of unfamiliarity with digital games.

The study sample consisted of 14 participants. Of these participants, 50% ($n=7$) were female, 42.9% ($n=6$) were male, and 7.1% ($n=1$) did not want to affirm their gender. The education level of the sample was divided equally into graduate ($n=7$) and

undergraduate ($n=7$). 14.3% ($n=2$) of the participants' age were between eighteen and twenty-five, 71.4% of them were between twenty-five and thirty-five, and 14.3% ($n=2$) of them were between thirty-five and forty-five. The participants' detailed demographic data is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Sample

		<i>N</i> =14	%
Gender	Female	7	50
	Male	6	42.9
	Do not want to affirm	1	7.1
Age	18-24	2	14.3
	25-34	10	71.4
	35-44	2	14.3
Education Level	Undergraduate	7	50
	Graduate	7	50
Employment	Full-Time Employed	10	71.4
	Unemployed	2	14.3
	Student	2	14.3
Socio-Economic Status	Low-Middle SES	1	7.1
	Middle SES	8	57.1
	Middle-High SES	4	28.6
	High SES	1	7.1
Game Played in Last Three Years	5-10 Games	4	28.6
	10-20 Games	4	28.6
	20 and more Games	6	42.8
Weekly Playing Hours	0-2 Hours	3	21.4
	2-5 Hours	3	21.4
	5-10 Hours	2	14.3
	10-20 Hours	4	28.6
	20 and more Hours	2	14.3

3.5 Data Collection

3.5.1 Data collection tools. The study utilizes various tools for data collection. During gameplay sessions, participants' play was observed, and their screen was recorded. The audio was not recorded, and the records will not be shared with any third party. The observational data was used to extend the analysis. A demographic form, which the researcher prepared, was used to categorize the participants into demographic groups. The form consists of questions about age group, gender, education level, occupation, socioeconomic status, and playing habits. The gameplay form (see Table 2) prepared by the researcher was used to understand participants' gameplay experience.

Table 2

Gameplay Questions

No of Question	Question
1	The game is fun.
2	The game feels unfair.
3	The game is too difficult.
4	The game is hard to learn.
5	The game is winnable with different strategies or tactics.
6	The game's interface was hard to use.
7	The game makes me forget about the outside world.

The Perceived Persuasiveness Scale (PPS) is a scale that includes multiple items and subscales. PPS was developed by Thomas, Masthoff, and Oren (2019) and measures the perceived persuasiveness of a message. The scale includes nine 7-point Likert scale items and three subscales, which are effectiveness, quality, and capability.

The Cronbach's Alpha of the items in the subscales is greater than 0.9 for each subscale. Cronbach's Alpha values, which are greater than 0.9, imply "excellent" reliability (George & Mallery, 2021, p.260). The validity of game analysis will be checked with gameplay statements such as; "The game feels unfair," "The game is too difficult," and "The game is winnable with multiple strategies." The statements check the validity of specific game balance types. Fairness, challenge vs. success, and meaningful choices are the game balance types that will be checked.

3.5.2 Data collection procedures. Participants were recruited with convenience sampling. Information about research, procedures and participants' rights was given to participants. The informed consent forms were presented via Google Forms to online participants and via Google Forms and physical paper to face-to-face participants.

After the informed consent was given, the participants played Half-Earth Socialism and The Fiscal Ship games on a computer. Each game took approximately thirty minutes to be played. The play order of the games was shuffled randomly. The researcher chose the "Fight Climate Change" goal in The Fiscal Ship to match the domains of the games. Gameplay sessions were recorded with Open Broadcasting Software or Xbox Game Bar, but the computer sounds or setting sounds were not recorded to protect participants' confidentiality. Games are played on the Firefox browser. While the participants were playing the tutorials of the games, the researcher explained the information in the tutorials to ensure that the participants learned how to play. After the tutorials, the researcher did not intervene in the gameplay.

After the gameplay session ended, participants filled out the demographic form, the PPS for each game, and the gameplay form for each game in the given order. Participants were reminded that the "Message" in the PPS means the game they have played.

3.5.3 Data analysis procedures. Qualitative data analysis will be used to analyze gathered data. The normality of the data will be checked to determine which tests will be used. Kurtosis and skewness values between -2.0 and +2.0 mean that the data distribution is sufficiently normal (George & Mallery, 2021, p.114). Parametric tests will be used for normal distributed data, and nonparametric tests will be used for

non-normal distributed data. The results of PPS for The Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism will be compared with each other. Each sub-scale of PPS for the games will be compared as well. Comparisons of PPS and its subscales will be used to assess the main hypothesis. The results of each item in gameplay form will be compared with those of the same item for the other game. Paired sample t-test or Wilcoxon test will be used for correlations between variables. Paired sample t-test will be used for normal distributed variables, and Wilcoxon for non-normal distributed variables.

Data analysis will be extended by examining the effects of demographic characteristics on perceived persuasiveness. Independent sample t-test will be used for samples with two values, such as “Do you play serious games?”, “Do you play card games?” “Are you interested in climate change?” and “Are you interested in fiscal policies?”. One-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) Test will be used for samples with more than two variables, such as age, gender, education level, occupation, socioeconomic status, and playing habits.

3.6 Limitations

While the research produces valuable insights about the effects of game balance on serious games, there are several possible limitations. The usage of convenience sampling might be one of the limitations. Convenience sampling is biased towards easily accessible participants and misses certain types of participants. It does not provide representative data (Haşiloğlu, Baran, & Aydın, 2015). The sample size is small relative to the population, but we utilize observations and surveys to acquire data effectively. There are several reasons why we were unable to increase the sample size. First, we have criteria for participants to include in the study. These criteria restrict the number of available participants. The main limiting factors of the sample size are the duration and logistics of data collection. Play sessions and surveys take approximately sixty and fifteen minutes. The room where the play session and the survey are conducted is arranged for the convenience of the participants. That means different locations and devices are prepared. These factors limit the number of participants. The research might be limited to detecting differences between age groups and employment status because 10 of 14 participants are between twenty-five and thirty-five years old, and 10 of 14 participants are full-time employed.

The study measures only the immediate effect of a play session. The duration of total play may affect the player differently, and the effects of the play may change with time. It neither assesses the effects of prolonged play nor the long-term effects of the play.

Even though games are chosen cautiously to minimize the effects of the game aspects other than game balance, the non-entertainment goal of the games might be affected by other game aspects such as the duration, the art style, and the playability of the game. We focused on the interaction between the game and the player. The game balance and the game perception are affected by the metagame. The study is unable to discuss the influence of the metagame. The research uses ten game balance types to compare the effectiveness of game balance, but each type might affect the non-entertainment goal separately. The research is unable to differentiate the effects of the individual game balance types. Balance analysis can determine which game is more balanced but does not determine how much more.

Another limitation of this research is the device that the games are played on. The research is limited to games that are played on computers, which restricts the understanding of game balance on mobile, console and board games. The games analyzed and play-tested are in the domain of climate change. The studied games might not speak for serious games in other domains.

Chapter 4

Findings

4.1 Game Analysis

4.1.1 The Fiscal Ship. Hutchins Center and Woodrow Wilson Center produce the Fiscal Ship, and the developer of the game is 1st Playable Production. The players choose tax and spending options to reduce the debt to today's level and meet the governing goals chosen at the beginning of the game (Hutchins Center & Woodrow Wilson Center, n.d.). The game won the Serious Play Gold Award (Newbury, 2017) and entered the Best Educational Apps for Kids list in the New York Post (Kaplan, 2020). The aim of the game is to teach people how the federal budget works. The federal budget is a complicated and vital topic (Sheiner, Wessel, & Pita, 2016; Wessel, 2016a). Budgeting is not merely a number management; each policy is supported by different people. Governing goals simulate the social aspect of budgeting (V. Lee, Schuele, & Sheiner, 2019). The game incorporates features that make it more suitable for classroom setup (Newbury, 2017).

The Fiscal Ship has over 100 fiscal policies in 17 categories and 12 governing goals that can be influenced. Adjusting these parameters is an important task. The most discussed policies are included in the game, and the data is gathered from government agencies and think tanks. Even the funders of the game do not have editorial control over the game (Hutchins Center & Woodrow Wilson Center, n.d.). The player needs to reduce the projected debt to GDP ratio from 126% to 75%. The economists discuss the optimal debt to GDP ratio; some think it should be low, and others should be higher. The game designers chose the 75% target to make the game more playable (Wessel, 2016b).

The Players choose three governing goals at the beginning of the game, which are also the game's winning conditions along with the debt target. The game's core mechanic is choosing a policy by clicking with the mouse. The game provides explanations and arguments about each policy. (Figure 8) Policies increase or decrease the debt and may affect the governing goal positively or negatively. The player can see the list of chosen policies and their effect on governing goals. Players can also remove the chosen policies. The game ends when the players submit their plans, or they

accomplish all their goals. The game allows players to play even after they have accomplished the goals. The end screen shows the most significant revenue-raising policies and most extensive spending-cutting policies. The end screen also provides the results for other governing goals.

Figure 8. Policy screen of Half-Earth Socialism.

David Wessel (2016c), the director of Hutchins Center on Fiscal & Monetary Policy, gives information about players' decisions. Ten of the fifteen most popular choices raise taxes. The three most popular choices are "carbon tax," "eliminate tax breaks for oil, gas, and coal," and "eliminate the taxable maximum in 2016 and later years," in the respective order. The three least popular choices are "implement a 15% flat tax," "cut individual tax rates to three brackets," and "eliminate interest, dividends, and capital gain taxes." He also says that 56% of the players are 18 to 34 years old.

4.1.1.1 Fairness. Even though The Fiscal Ship is a single-player game, however symmetry is not irrelevant. The symmetry between policies needs to be considered. The impact of policies on debt and governing goals varies. Some policies barely change the debt, and some change the debt in such a way that the game becomes nearly unwinnable without removing that policy. For instance, "Provide Universal Basic Income" doubles the starting debt. Choosing the wrong policy may seem unfair, but the graph shows the new debt before choosing the policy, and the player can

remove the policy whenever they want. The core play of the game is reading the policies' explanation and deciding if the policy is favorable. Every policy has an explanation, supporting and opposing arguments, and the length of the texts are similar. The deciding process of the game is symmetrical for all policies. We can say that the game has symmetric and asymmetric parts, and it is fair.

4.1.1.2 Challenge vs. success. The Challenge of the game is understanding simple texts that explain complex topics and deciding their effects on the governing goals. The game is not very challenging. The target population of the game includes primary school students (V. Lee et al., 2019), so the game had to be easy. Keeping the difficulty at the same level throughout the game is not the optimal way to balance the game. The game does not accommodate a variety of challenges. Choosing governing goals at the start of the game works as difficulty selection. Players can combine synergic goals such as “Strengthen Social Safety Net” and “Reduce Inequality” to play an easier game or combine contradictory goals to increase the difficulty.

4.1.1.3 Meaningful choices. The choices in the game have a variety of outcomes, and some of them have more impact on the debt than others. The impactful policies can be called dominant strategies, but the game minimizes the adverse effects of dominant strategies. The players need a multitude of policies to reach the debt goal, so the players need to discover other policies to reach the debt goal.

The players also need to reach governing goals to win the game. Policies do not contribute to all governing goals. Some policies become meaningless for certain configurations of governing goals, but players usually ignore them. For example, if the player chose “Strengthen National Defense” and “Protect The Elderly” as governing goals, they would pass the “Cut Funding for Energy Research”. The meaningless policies become meaningful when the player plays the game again. This design decision makes the game more replayable.

4.1.1.4 Skill vs. chance. The Fiscal Ship is a skill game except the optional random goals in the governing goal selection screen. Casual games use chance more commonly. A serious game that intends to persuade should be trustworthy, so chance should be used cautiously in a serious game. The game is also designed to be played

and discussed in the classrooms (V. Lee et al., 2019), so the game experience needs to be the same for everybody in the classroom. The Fiscal Ship aligns with its aim and target audience by being skill-based.

4.1.1.5 Short vs. long. The Fiscal Ship takes a short time to complete. Short games may reach more people easily because of the modest time requirement. The game would allow the players to develop strategies if it was longer. Short vs. Long is a tradeoff for The Fiscal Ship. The game can be longer with new mechanics so that the players will develop strategies. However, the new mechanics require correct data and projection from the real world. Unbiased projections are challenging to find if there are any unbiased projections. Being short is somewhat better for The Fiscal Ship.

4.1.1.6 Rewards. The Fiscal Ship presents rewards in various ways. The progress of debt, shown on the screen during the play, serves as points that motivate the players. Players can express themselves by choosing policies that align with their political views. The current status of governing goals is shown with stars. Each star is a reward, and the governing goal is completed when the player achieves three stars. This kind of completion is not a powerful reward because the player can lose the stars, so achieving three stars does not provide a sense of closure. The effect of getting stars is enhanced by sound effects.

Varying the amount of rewards is more impactful than fixed rewards. The players do not know the policy's effect on governing goals before they choose it. After the players choose a policy, they check the effects, which can be insignificant or game changing. Varying results in governing goals excite players more. Increasing the rewards prevents players from getting used to the rewards. The amount of rewards does not increase during the game, but this does not cause a problem because the game is not long enough to have inflated rewards.

4.1.1.7 Punishment. The Fiscal Ship only comprises limited punishments. When the players choose the wrong policy, a red arrow shows that the chosen policy affects the governing goal adversely. The game has red crosses, which are the opposite of stars, but the red crosses are only shown at the end screen.

4.1.1.8 Freedom vs. controlled experience. The game leans towards a controlled experience. The game does not provide the players with the freedom to manipulate the policies. However, extended freedom would not only complicate the game but would also move the game away from real-world data. The experience can be improved by increasing the control. The game has more than a hundred policies. Players can be bored by navigating policies unrelated to their governing goals. The game can curate the navigation by highlighting related policies. However, highlighting specific policies would make the game biased. The Fiscal Ship is well balanced in the context of freedom and controlled experience because moving towards only for either end worsens the game.

4.1.1.9 Simple vs. complex. The analysis method focuses on the complexity of the games, but we can still use it to analyze The Fiscal Ship. The Fiscal Ship is simple but more complex than a casual mobile game. The players need to comprehend complex topics, and the game aims to reach a broad audience, so being simple in terms of mechanics is favorable. The innate complexity of the topic prevents the game from being too simple.

4.1.1.10 Detail vs. imagination. The game is not visually detailed. The visual clues are the pictograms of governing goals and the ship. The details neither help the imagination nor prevent it. The details help players to understand the game. The textual details help players comprehend the basic idea of the policy and tell the disagreeing arguments so the player can imagine the policy from varying points of view. In summary, visual details are not good or bad, and textual details are favorable.

4.1.2 Half-Earth Socialism. The Half-Earth Socialism is originally a semi-scientific utopian book by Troy Vettese and Drew Pendergrass (2022). The authors claim that they wrote the book to propose new alternative solutions to the climate crisis because the mainstream solutions are either too soft or too dangerous. It aims to envision a desirable, feasible and necessary new society. The book uses several science fields, including ecology, energy studies, epidemiology, and biogeography, to reach conclusions. They argue that some solutions are infeasible, for example, lab-grown meat, electric cars, wildlife conservation, and geoengineering schemes. They also

argue that some solutions are effective, for instance, widespread veganism, energy quotas, marketless planning, and socialist democracy (Pendergrass & Vettese, n.d.).

The Half-Earth Socialism game is adapted from the book mentioned above. Numerous designers, researchers, and artists worked on the game, but Francis Tseng is the main developer, and Son La Pham is the main designer. The players who play the game become the world leader who tries to solve the climate crisis. The game provides plentiful research, infrastructure, and policy options from different ideologies to decide. The game calculates the effects of the decisions with the real climate model HECTOR (Pendergrass & Vettese, n.d.).

The Half-Earth Socialism presents its goals at the beginning of the game. The players need to take care of political capital, biodiversity pressure, contentedness, temperature anomaly, and emission values. Political capital is the currency players use; it needs to be above zero; otherwise, the game ends. Contentedness needs to be above zero, like political capital. Other parameters do not directly end the game, but players are required to reach a certain threshold to win the game. Other parameters are also kept in the game, such as land use, energy use, water stress, sea level rise, population, living standards, habitability, fuel use, animal calories, and plant calories. However, these parameters are not as influential as others. The game evolves in turns, which is represented by planning cycles. Between each planning cycle, the players can enact plans or change productions. At the end of each cycle, the players face events and see the results of their actions. They gain or lose political power based on their performance. Figure 9 shows the interaction diagram of the game elements.

Figure 9. Half-Earth Socialism game diagram.

The players can enact plans and change production (Figure 10). They can enact plans in three categories: Research, infrastructure, and policies. The players need to spend political capital to enact a plan. Research and infrastructure plans need time to complete, and the player can spend more political capital to accelerate the completion. Policies are executed in the next planning cycle but require more political power. Each plan has its unique property. It can be as specific as changing the value of a production or as general as changing contentedness. There are four domains of production: Electricity, fuel, plant calories, and animal calories. Each domain has its own options, such as coal, biofuel, grey hydrogen, natural gas, and so on. The options have different energy, water, biodiversity pressure, land use, and emission values. The players can decrease the percentage of one option to increase the percentage of the other one.

Figure 10. Plans and productions tabs of Half-Earth Socialism.

The Half-Earth Socialism also has government, statistics, and world tabs (Figure 11, 12, and 13). The player can not act in these tabs. The players can see the political parties in the parliament in the government tab. Production changes and enacted plans change the political parties' attitude toward the player. An allied political party provides bonuses and objectives. The statistics tab provides extended information about the values of the game system. In the world tab, the player can see the properties of each region of the world, such as the fuel demand of Southern Asia.

Figure 11. Government tab of Half-Earth Socialism.

Figure 12. Statistics tab of Half-Earth Socialism.

Figure 13. World tab of Half-Earth Socialism.

4.1.2.1 Fairness. Half-Earth Socialism is a single-player game, but symmetry is still a subject of analysis. Game elements such as plans need to be inspected. Research plans affect many other game elements, such as political parties, production, industries, plans and variables. We can see the effects of research plans on the political parties in Figure 14. It is obvious that the Environmentalists are positively affected by the research plans, and Consumerists are negatively affected. Malthusians and Ecofeminists are hard to interact with when using research plans. An asymmetrical game system may provide exciting gameplay, but in this case, it restricts the gameplay by undermining game elements.

Figure 14. Research-political party graph of Half-Earth Socialism.

4.1.2.2 Challenge vs. success. The developers of Half-Earth Socialism did not reveal their target audience, but the game needs to reach a broad audience to materialize their alternative solutions. The game's difficulty is typical for a 4X game, but a 4X game appeals to a niche player base. The game is too difficult for regular players. The game does not provide any difficulty selection to engage different players. The game's main challenge is solving the game system and developing a strategy. The level of challenge should increase to keep players engaged. The game starts with a generous 100 political capital to enable players to enact the plans they want. After the first planning cycle, players earn or lose political capital based on their performance. Some players lose political capital after the first cycle, which leads to a loss, and on the contrary, some players earn more than a hundred political capital, which makes the game easier. The difficulty curve of the game fluctuates between different tries. We

can expect the player to lose the game on the first try, but the game becomes easy for an experienced player, especially at the end of the game.

4.1.2.3 Meaningful choices. The choices in the game affect various game elements. Some of these game elements barely influence the winning conditions. For instance, “Biofabrication” only reduces the CO2 emission of chemicals, and the tooltip in the game can not show the number because the decrease is too insignificant to show. “Regenerative Agriculture” increases soil supply along with other effects, but the game does not track this value (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Biofabrication and regenerative agriculture plans.

The game presents many choices to the player. A high number of choices usually empower the players. However, in this case, it confuses the player because the choices are complex and presented without preparing the players. The excessive number of choices would have been more effective if they had been presented separately. A balanced game should not have dominant strategies. However, in this game, some choices are much stronger than others. For example, “Feminist Science and Technology Studies” provides twenty research points and one contentedness. Twenty research points are equal to sixty political capitals. It is exceptionally advantageous over other plans, but the player needs to enact more than one plan, so the negative effect of the dominant strategy is reduced. Production is more susceptible to dominant strategies. Wind power is better than other electricity production methods, and the players can convert all electricity production to wind power. It can be said that the game does not provide enough meaningful choices.

4.1.2.4 Skill vs. chance. The Half-Earth Socialism is mostly skill-based, but the events between the planning cycles are based on chance (Figure 16). The player can lower the probability of the events. It is a satisfying example of using skill and chance together to find balance.

Figure 16. An event in Half-Earth Socialism.

4.1.2.5 Short vs. long. Half-Earth Socialism is long compared to The Fiscal Ship. Half-Earth Socialism requires more time commitment, which shrinks its audience. However, longer games allow players to develop strategies. The game will end in the early cycles if the player loses the game. Losing the game demotivates players. The game provides one-time protection against losing because of depleted political capital. When the player loses all political capital, a hero arrives and gives

fifty political capital. This protection is beneficial for keeping the player in the game, but more is needed. Low contentedness is also a frequent way to lose the game.

4.1.2.6 Rewards. The game has several rewards. The political parties praise the players if the player is allied with them. At the end of the cycle, the game gives political capital to the player if the player performs well, but this reward is not guaranteed. Lowering the emissions and the extinction rate can be considered as points, which is a form of reward. The players can express themselves by working with a political party they approve of in real life.

Players need to understand that they received a reward. In the playtests, some players get confused by the report (Figure 17) from the previous cycle. They did not understand how they performed and how their performance affected the political capital. The abundance of the rewards is also vital. All rewards in the game are presented at the start of the planning cycle. Frequent rewards would motivate the players.

Figure 17. Cycle report in Half-Earth Socialism.

4.1.2.7 Punishment. The game has punishment versions for almost every reward that it presents. Rival parties and the Earth Liberation Front shame the player for different reasons. The game takes away political capital if the player does not perform well. Parameters like emissions can rise in the game just like they can decrease. Especially the temperature anomaly increases in the early planning cycles, and the players do not have any immediate solutions for the temperature anomaly. Most events are used as punishments in the game; for example, new mosquito-borne disease, forest infested, mountain gorilla declared extinct, wildfires, and flooding. The Punishments in the game try to describe the severity of the climate crisis. The game prefers punishments over rewards, and punishments are not balanced with powerful rewards.

4.1.2.8 Freedom vs. controlled experience. Half-Earth Socialism allows players to choose from a wide range of plans and productions. Some plans have insignificant effects on the game system. Irrelevant actions weaken the gameplay. Even impactful plans feel insignificant because of the long implementation time of the plans.

4.1.2.9 Simple vs. complex. Half-Earth Socialism contains plenty of plans that can affect every type of game element, more than twenty production industries that can affect at least five parameters, nine political parties, and at least ten parameters. The game is inarguably complex, but its complexity is not emergent. The rule set of the game is as complex as the game itself. Games with simple rules and complex play are considered more favorable.

4.1.2.10 Detail vs. imagination. The pictures in the game are detailed. They may prevent players from imagining the plan or the production differently. However, the pictograms of the characters, such as political parties, are abstract and simple. The pictograms boost the players' imagination. The texts in the game are generally short and informative, so they are better at enhancing the imagination. However, the dialog boxes create a narrative and can boost the imagination.

4.1.3 Comparison of the games. According to our analysis, Half-Earth Socialism only performs better than The Fiscal Ship on "Details vs. Imagination." The games achieve similar performance on "Skill vs. Chance" and "Freedom vs.

Complexity.” The Fiscal Ship is better on all other balance types. Even though Half-Earth Socialism is better on some balance types, The Fiscal Ship is generally well-balanced (Table 3).

Table 3

Balance Type Analysis

Balance Type	The Fiscal Ship	Half-Earth Socialism
Fairness	✓	X
Challenge vs. Success	–	X
Meaningful Choices	–	X
Skill vs. Chance	✓	✓
Short vs. Long	✓	X
Rewards	✓	–
Punishment	✓	X
Freedom vs. Controlled Experience	✓	X
Simple vs. Complex	–	–
Detail vs. Imagination	–	✓

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Data screening. Before data analysis, the PPS and gameplay form results were explored with IBM SPSS v29.0.2.0 for missing values, normality, and reliability. The examination showed that the data does not have missing values. Table 4 shows that the PPS and PPS’s effectiveness subscale is normally distributed. Quality and capability subscales are not normally distributed with The Fiscal Ship’s quality subscale (Kurtosis=2.24, Skewness=-1.14) and The Fiscal Ship’s capability subscale (Kurtosis=2.80, Skewness=-1.46). The Cronbach’s Alpha of each subscale is calculated to check the reliability of the results. Cronbach’s Alpha score of each subscale is greater than 0.9, which indicates that the subscales are internally consistent. The number of each demographic subgroup is reviewed, and demographic subgroups with one participant are removed from the demographic group analysis. Removed subgroups are “Do not want to affirm” (Gender), High SES, and Low-Middle SES.

Table 4

The Descriptive Analysis of Perceived Persuasiveness Scale Results

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Cronbach's Alpha		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Fiscal Ship Effectiveness	14	3.14	1.68	2.82	-0.23	0.60	-1.71	1.15	0.99
Fiscal Ship Quality	14	4.90	1.53	2.35	-1.14	0.60	2.24	1.15	0.97
Fiscal Ship Capability	14	4.62	1.36	1.86	-1.46	0.60	2.80	1.15	0.92
Fiscal Ship PPS	14	4.22	0.90	0.82	-0.04	0.60	-1.61	1.15	
Half Earth Socialism Effectiveness	14	3.07	1.75	3.08	0.29	0.60	-1.47	1.15	0.97
Half Earth Socialism Quality	14	4.57	1.52	2.30	-0.38	0.60	-1.08	1.15	0.96
Half Earth Socialism Capability	14	5.02	1.52	2.30	-0.78	0.60	0.17	1.15	0.96
Half Earth Socialism PPS	14	4.22	1.33	1.78	-0.52	0.60	-1.02	1.15	

Table 5 shows that gameplay results are normally distributed except for “The Fiscal Ship is hard to learn” statement (Kurtosis=5.23, Skewness=1.93) and “Half-Earth Socialism is too difficult” statement (Kurtosis=2.77, Skewness=-0.89).

Table 5

The Descriptive Analysis of Gameplay Questionnaire Results

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Fiscal Ship is fun	14	4.57	1.91	3.65	-0.59	0.60	-0.73	1.15
Fiscal Ship feels unfair	14	2.79	1.72	2.95	0.60	0.60	-1.01	1.15
Fiscal Ship is too difficult	14	2.43	1.70	2.88	0.97	0.60	-0.24	1.15
Fiscal Ship is hard to learn	14	2.00	1.04	1.08	1.93	0.60	5.23	1.15
Fiscal Ship is winnable with multiple strategies	14	5.64	1.01	1.02	-0.19	0.60	-0.82	1.15
Fiscal Ship's UI is hard to use	14	2.00	0.68	0.46	0.00	0.60	-0.39	1.15
Fiscal Ship makes me forget the outside world	14	2.93	1.90	3.61	0.75	0.60	-0.33	1.15
Half Earth Socialism is fun	14	4.57	1.87	3.50	-0.42	0.60	-1.26	1.15
Half Earth Socialism feels unfair	14	3.86	1.56	2.44	0.56	0.60	-0.52	1.15
Half Earth Socialism is too difficult	14	5.14	1.23	1.51	-0.89	0.60	2.77	1.15
Half Earth Socialism is hard to learn	14	4.86	1.66	2.75	-0.57	0.60	-0.68	1.15
Half Earth Socialism is winnable with multiple strategies	14	4.71	1.59	2.53	0.01	0.60	-1.19	1.15
Half Earth Socialism's UI is hard to use	14	4.21	1.81	3.26	-0.10	0.60	-1.62	1.15
Half Earth Socialism makes me forget the outside world	14	3.21	1.81	3.26	0.82	0.60	0.00	1.15

4.2.2 Comparison of the means of the PPS scores. The difference between the PPS scores of the Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism is analyzed using paired sample t-test and Wilcoxon test. The paired Sample t-test is used for normally distributed data, and the Wilcoxon test is used for non-normally distributed data. The results are shown in Table 6. Only relevant p-values are shown in the table. The results demonstrate that the differences between the means are not statistically significant.

Table 6

Comparison Between the Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism on PPS

	The Fiscal Ship		Half-Earth Socialism		Significance	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic		<i>Wilcoxon</i>
PPS	4.22	0.90	4.22	1.33		1.000
Effectiveness	3.14	1.68	3.07	1.75		0.806
Quality	4.90	1.53	4.57	1.52	0.850	
Capability	4.62	1.36	5.02	1.52	0.180	

4.2.3 Comparison of the gameplay form scores. The difference between the gameplay form scores of the Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism is analyzed using paired sample t-test and Wilcoxon test. The paired Sample t-test is used for normally distributed data, and the Wilcoxon test is used for non-normally distributed data. Table 7 shows the results. Only relevant p-values are shown in the table. The results show that Half-Earth Socialism is more difficult ($z = -3.32, p = .001$), harder to learn ($z = -2.97, p = .001$), and its UI is harder to use ($t(13) = -4.12, p = .001$). The games are equivalently fun and immersive. Half-Earth Socialism makes players feel more unfair, but the difference is not statistically significant. The players think The Fiscal Ship can be won with more strategies, but the difference is not statistically significant.

Table 7

Comparison Between the Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism on Gameplay Form

	The Fiscal Ship		Half-Earth Socialism		Significance	Paired Sample T-Test
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Wilcoxon	
The Game is fun	4.57	1.91	4.57	1.87		1.000
The Game feels unfair	2.79	1.72	3.86	1.56		0.132
The Game is too difficult	2.43	1.70	5.14	1.23	0.001	
The Game is hard to learn	2.00	1.04	4.86	1.66	0.001	
The Game is winnable with multiple strategies	5.64	1.01	4.71	1.59		0.060
The Game's UI is hard to use	2.00	0.68	4.21	1.81		0.001
The Game makes me forget the outside world	2.93	1.90	3.21	1.81		0.618

4.2.4 Demographic group analysis. If the demographic groups consist of two subgroups, their PPS scores of the games are analyzed with independent sample t-test. Participants have either an undergraduate degree or a graduate degree. Gender and SES have subgroups with only one participant, and subgroups with one participant are removed from this analysis. Thus, gender, education level, and socio-economic status are analyzed with independent sample t-test. The analysis results are shown in Table 8. The analysis indicates that the differences are insignificant. Gender, Education Level, and Socio-Economic Status do not affect players' perceived persuasiveness of examined games.

Table 8

Comparison Between the Subgroups on Perceived Persuasiveness Scale

		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>
Fiscal Ship PPS	Male	6	3.87	1.00	0.29
	Female	7	4.43	0.83	
Half Earth Socialism PPS	Male	6	3.74	1.28	0.36
	Female	7	4.44	1.38	
Fiscal Ship PPS	Undergraduate	7	4.13	0.94	0.71
	Graduate	7	4.32	0.93	
Half Earth Socialism PPS	Undergraduate	7	4.14	1.35	0.83
	Graduate	7	4.30	1.42	
Fiscal Ship PPS	Middle SES	8	4.14	0.95	0.36
	Middle-High SES	4	4.67	0.74	
Half Earth Socialism PPS	Middle SES	8	4.00	1.55	0.45
	Middle-High SES	4	4.70	1.16	

Age, employment, number of games played in the last three years, and weekly gaming hours are analyzed with one-way ANOVA test. The results are shown in the table 9, 10, 11, and 12, respectively. One-way ANOVA demonstrated that the effects of age ($F(2,11) = 1.02, p = .392$), employment ($F(2,11) = 1.23, p = .331$), number of games played ($F(2,11) = 1.22, p = .332$), and weekly gaming hours ($F(4,9) = 1.14, p = .396$) on The Fiscal Ship are insignificant. The effects of age ($F(2,11) = 0.47, p = .639$), employment ($F(2,11) = 0.70, p = .519$), number of games played ($F(2,11) = 0.22, p = .806$), and weekly gaming hours ($F(4,9) = 0.53, p = .719$) on the Half-Earth Socialism are insignificant.

Table 9

Comparison Between the Age Groups on Perceived Persuasiveness Scale

		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>
Fiscal Ship Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	18-24	2	5.1	0.1	0.39
	25-34	10	4.1	0.9	
	35-44	2	3.9	1.5	
	Total	14	4.2	0.9	
Half Earth Socialism Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	18-24	2	5.0	0.9	0.64
	25-34	10	4.0	1.4	
	35-44	2	4.5	1.5	
	Total	14	4.2	1.3	

Table 10

Comparison Between the Employment Groups on Perceived Persuasiveness Scale

		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>
Fiscal Ship Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	Unemployed	2	3.7	1.0	0.33
	Full time employed	10	4.2	0.9	
	Student	2	5.1	0.1	
	Total	14	4.2	0.9	
Half Earth Socialism Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	Unemployed	2	3.4	2.1	0.52
	Full time employed	10	4.2	1.3	
	Student	2	5.0	0.9	
	Total	14	4.2	1.3	

Table 11

Comparison Between the Number of Games Played Groups on Perceived Persuasiveness Scale

		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>
Fiscal Ship Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	5-10	4	3.7	0.9	0.33
	10-20	4	4.1	1.0	
	More than 20	6	4.6	0.8	
	Total	14	4.2	0.9	
Half Earth Socialism Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	5-10	4	3.9	1.2	0.81
	10-20	4	4.1	1.8	
	More than 20	6	4.5	1.3	
	Total	14	4.2	1.3	

Table 12

Comparison Between the Weekly Playing Hours Groups on Perceived Persuasiveness Scale

		<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>p</i>
Fiscal Ship Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	0-2 hours	3	4.5	0.7	0.40
	2-5 hours	3	4.9	0.9	
	5-10 hours	2	3.2	0.5	
	10-20 hours	4	4.1	0.9	
	More than 20 hours	2	4.0	1.4	
	Total	14	4.2	0.9	
Half Earth Socialism Perceived Persuasiveness Scale	0-2 hours	3	4.9	1.3	0.72
	2-5 hours	3	3.9	1.8	
	5-10 hours	2	3.3	0.2	
	10-20 hours	4	4.6	0.9	
	More than 20 hours	2	3.7	2.6	
	Total	14	4.2	1.3	

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusions

This research aimed to explore the effects of game balance on additional goals of serious games. To achieve this aim, we analyzed The Fiscal Ship and Half-Earth Socialism to evaluate their balance; then, we conducted a playtest session and survey with fourteen participants. The playtesters played each game for at least half an hour and, at most, one hour. The survey conducted consists of demographic questions, PPS, and gameplay questions. In this chapter, we compare the game balance evaluation and survey results.

5.1 Discussion

Our game balance analysis yields results in favor of The Fiscal Ship. The Fiscal Ship is considerably better than Half-Earth Socialism in terms of fairness, short vs. long, punishment, and freedom vs. controlled experience. The Fiscal Ship is slightly better on challenge vs success, meaningful choices, and rewards. The games performed similarly on skill vs. chance, and simple vs. complex. The only field Half-Earth Socialism is better at is detail vs. imagination. The analysis was supported with playtest statements.

Three game balance categories are checked with play test statements. Two statements checked the challenge vs. success category. The statements are “The game is too difficult.” and “The game is hard to learn.” The Fiscal Ship’s score was $M = 2.4$, $SD = 1.7$ and $M = 2.0$, $SD = 1.0$, respectively. Half-Earth Socialism’s score was $M = 5.1$, $SD = 1.2$ and $M = 4.9$, $SD = 1.7$, respectively. The Wilcoxon test was used to determine the significance of the difference between the means. The results of “The game is too difficult” ($z = -3.32$, $p = .001$) and “The game is hard to learn” ($z = -2.97$, $p = .001$) showed that the challenge vs. success analysis is correct.

Fairness is checked with “The game feels unfair” statement. The Fiscal Ship’s score was $M = 2.8$, $SD = 1.7$. Half-Earth Socialism’s score was $M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.6$. Even though there is a 1.1-point difference between the means, the paired sample t-test ($t(13) = -1.61$, $p = .13$) demonstrates that the difference is not significant. Meaningful choices are checked with “The game is winnable with multiple strategies.” statement. The Fiscal Ship’s score was $M = 5.6$, $SD = 1.0$. Half-Earth Socialism’s

score was $M = 4.7$, $SD = 1.6$. although there is a 0.9-point difference between the means, the paired sample t-test ($t(13) = 2.06$, $p = .06$) displayed that the difference is not significant. Even though the participants thought similarly to the analyst, we can not assume it is not coincidental.

The main research question is, "Does game balance affect the additional goal of serious games?" To answer this question, we conducted a PPS survey with the playtesters of the selected games. After we gathered the data, the PPS means of the selected games were compared with the paired sample t-test. The difference between the two games' PPS ($t(13) = 0.00$, $p = 1.00$) scores is insignificant. Notably, the games' mean PPS scores are the same. The results could not prove that the game balance affects the additional goals of the serious games.

The second research question is, "How does game balance affect the different aspects of persuasive goals, such as effectiveness, quality, and capability?" We compared the means of PPS's subscale scores to answer this question. The means were compared with a paired sample t-test and Wilcoxon test. The difference between the effectiveness subscale ($t(13) = 0.25$, $p = .81$), quality subscale ($z = -0.19$, $p = .85$), and capability subscale ($z = -1.34$, $p = .18$) scores of the two games are not significant. The capability score is the most promising one, but it is also insignificant.

The third research question is, "Are demographic groups affected by serious games differently?" To answer this question, we gathered the participants' demographic data and compared them with an independent sample t-test and ANOVA. P values of the t-tests vary between $p = .29$ and $p = .83$. Thus, the games do not diversely affect the players of different gender, education levels, and SES groups. P values of ANOVA tests vary between $p = .33$ and $p = .81$. Thus, the games do not diversely affect the players in different employment, weekly gaming hours, played games, and age groups.

The gameplay form contains statements such as "The game is fun." "The game's interface was hard to use," and "The game makes me forget about the outside world." Evaluation of both games with these questions compared with a paired sample t-test. Both games are equally fun ($t(13) = 0.00$, $p = 1.00$). The UI of the Half-Earth Socialism is significantly more difficult to use ($t(13) = -4.13$, $p < .001$). The UI design

problems are related to the usability of the game. It may affect the perception of players on various subjects, such as complexity, difficulty, and fairness. A discrete level of usability may hinder the validity of the research. “The game makes me forget about the outside world” statement aims to measure the immersiveness of the game. A similar level of player immersion means players were similarly focused on the game. Thus, the results were not affected by players’ loss of attention. This particular result helps to ensure the validity of the research.

5.2 Conclusions

Previous research (Becker & Görlich, 2020) and our literature review agree that game balance research on serious games is limited in the literature. Our study is one of the first ones that explores the relationship between the success of a serious game and game balance. Thus, comparing our results with those of earlier studies is difficult. While game balance is crucial for entertainment games’ success (Andrade et al., 2021), it is intuitive to consider it critical for serious games, but our results suggest the contrary.

Kraaijenbrink et al. (2009) conducted a study with interactive board games, and they demonstrated that balanced games increase the fun players have. On the other hand, Rubin and DeCoster (2018) claim that balance is the enemy of fun because imbalance creates exciting situations. Our results on the “The game is fun” statement did not find a significant relationship between fun and balance.

We tested meaningful choices, difficulty and fairness with balance analysis and gameplay form. Even though all are different in the analysis, only the difficulty has compelling results from data analysis. Game designers in the industry may focus on the difficulty while balancing their game to get more from their limited resources.

5.3 Recommendations for Future Research

Serious game and game balance are novel fields of research. The literature still needs groundwork for future studies. Debates about game balance may be caused by diverse definitions of game balance. A new game balance definition would amplify the problem, but a definition analysis that shows the strengths and the weaknesses of definitions of different types of games can be beneficial. Measuring the success of a serious game is a common theme for serious game research. Researchers adopt

measurement tools from other science fields, such as psychology and education. However, measurement tools specifically for digital game design can produce more accurate data. Future researchers can still use the knowledge from other fields while developing new tools, such as Learning types from education and Persuasion models from psychology.

Measuring game balance is more challenging than measuring the success of a serious game. There are attempts to measure balance mathematically, such as Machinations (Dormans, 2011; Jaffe, 2013). These tools are useful for developing games, but simulating different games requires different abstraction levels, and different abstraction levels may lead to incorrect measurement. A framework for simulating games helps to produce more reliable data. Although mathematical balance is crucial, the game balance can only be evaluated with players. A quantitative measurement tool incorporating players may accelerate the game balance research. The metagame or the media around the game is also essential to understand the game balance, especially for competitive multiplayer games.

Experimental research is valuable because it is better for finding causation. However, in game research, changing one independent variable is challenging. The best way to do this is to develop games for research. Developing games for the research may only be possible sometimes. While experimenting with already developed games, the researcher may improve the validity by checking the possible changes in extraneous variables. Finding causation in experiments requires a high number of participants. Conducting a study with more participants would also increase the representation of the population. However, the number of participants is tied to the resources available to researchers.

The effects of prolonged play and the long-term effects of play are still an open area to uncover. The potential positive and negative effects of prolonged play may increase, decrease, or stay the same throughout the prolonged play. Determining the optimal play duration is influential because it may change the serious games' design by shifting their target playtime. The effects of play are expected to diminish after a play session, but this expectation requires new studies to conclude. Furthermore, the rate of

diminishing effects may guide designers in determining the intervals at which serious games should be played.

Game balance has separate concepts, such as fairness, difficulty, and meaningful choices. Each concept may have different effects on games. Researchers may expand the game balance knowledge by studying these concepts.

REFERENCES

- 1st Playable Productions. (2016). *The Fiscal Ship* (PC Version).
- Adams, E. (2010). *Fundamentals of game design* (2nd ed.). Berkeley: New Riders.
- Adams, E., & Dormans, Joris. (2012). *Game Mechanics : Advanced Game Design*. New Riders.
- Adams, E., & Rollings, A. (2003). *Andrew Rollings and Ernest Adams on Game Design* (1st ed.). New Riders Publishing.
- Andrade, G., Ramalho, G., Gomes, A. S., & Corruble, V. (2021). Dynamic Game Balancing: an Evaluation of User Satisfaction. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment*, 2(1), 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aiide.v2i1.18739>
- Becker, A., & Görlich, D. (2020). What is Game Balancing? - An Examination of Concepts. *ParadigmPlus*, 1(1), 22–41. <https://doi.org/10.55969/paradigmplus.v1n1a2>
- Brathwaite, Brenda., & Schreiber, Ian. (2009). *Challenges for game designers*. Charles River Media, a part of Course Technology.
- Browne, C. (2008). *Automatic Generation and Evaluation of Recombination Games* (Doctoral Dissertation). Queensland University of Technology.
- Bungie. (2017). *Destiny 2* (PC Version).
- Burda, Y., Edwards, H., Pathak, D., Storkey, A., Darrell, T., & Efros, A. A. (2019). Large-Scale Study of Curiosity-Driven Learning. *ICLR*.
- Burgun, K. (2011). Understanding Balance in Video Games. Retrieved December 17, 2023, from <https://www.gamedeveloper.com/design/understanding-balance-in-video-games>
- Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1990). *Flow: The Psychology of Optimal Experience*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/224927532>

- Dormans, J. (2011). Simulating Mechanics to Study Emergence in Games The Machinations Framework. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment*, 2–7.
- Dörner, R., Göbel, S., & Effelsberg, W. (2016). *Serious Games Foundations, Concepts and Practice* (R. Dörner, S. Göbel, W. Effelsberg, & J. Wiemeyer, Eds.). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40612-1>
- Entertainment Software Association. (2023). Power of Play - Global Report. Retrieved May 10, 2024, from <https://www.theesa.com/resources/power-of-play-global-report-2023/>
- Felder, D. (2015, November 12). Design 101: Balancing Games What makes a broken game? How do you make a balanced one quickly and efficiently? Stay Updated. Retrieved December 17, 2023, from <https://www.gamedeveloper.com/design/design-101-balancing-games>
- Firaxis Games. (2016). X-Com 2 (PC Version).
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2021). *IBM SPSS Statistics 27 Step by Step* (17th ed.). New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003205333>
- Giovannetti, A. (2019, March). Slay The Spire: Metric Driven Design and Balance. Retrieved January 25, 2024, from Game Developers Conference website: <https://www.gdcvault.com/play/1025731/-Slay-the-Spire-Metrics>
- Giunti, G., Baum, A., Giunti, D., Plazzotta, F., Benitez, S., Gomez, A., ... Bernaldo, F. G. (2015). *Serious Games: A Concise Overview on What They Are and Their Potential Applications to Healthcare*. <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-564-7-386>
- Hamari, J., & Tuunanen, J. (2014). *Player Types: A Meta-synthesis*.
- Haşiloğlu, S. B., Baran, T., & Aydın, O. (2015). A study on the potential problems in marketing research: convenience sampling and scale items with adverbs of frequency. *Pamukkale Journal of Business and Information Management*, 2(1), 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.5505/piby.2015.47966>

- Hsu, S. H., Wen, M.-H., & Wu, M.-C. (2007). Exploring Design Features for Enhancing Players' Challenge in Strategy Games. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 10(3), 393–397. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2006.9940>
- Huizinga, J. (2014). *Homo Ludens: a study of the play element in culture*. Boston: The Beacon Press.
- Hutchins Center, & Woodrow Wilson Center. (n.d.). The Fiscal Ship + FAQ. Retrieved April 19, 2024, from <https://fiscalship.org/faq.php#faq09>
- Jaffe, A. (2013). *Understanding Game Balance with Quantitative Methods* (Doctoral Dissertation). University of Washington.
- Jaffe, A. (2015). Metagame Balance. Retrieved January 27, 2024, from Game Developers Conference website: <https://www.gdcvault.com/play/1022155/Metagame>
- Kaplan, M. (2020, March 16). The best educational apps for kids to game during coronavirus. *New York Post*. Retrieved from <https://nypost.com/2020/03/16/the-best-educational-apps-for-kids-to-game-during-coronavirus/>
- Kraaijenbrink, E., Van Gils, F., Cheng, Q., Van Herk, R., & Van Den Hoven, E. (2009). Balancing Skills to Optimize Fun in Interactive Board Games. *LNCS*, 5726, 301–313.
- Laamarti, F., Eid, M., & El Saddik, A. (2014). An overview of serious games. *International Journal of Computer Games Technology*, Vol. 2014. Hindawi Publishing Corporation. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/358152>
- Lee, V., Schuele, F., & Sheiner, L. (2019). *The Fiscal Ship as a Teaching Tool*. Retrieved from <https://www.brookings.edu/research/the-fiscal-ship-as-a-teaching-tool/>
- Mayo, D. (2018, March). Board Game Design Day: Balancing Mechanics for Your Card Game's Unique "Power Curve." Retrieved January 27, 2024, from Game Developers Conference website: <https://www.gdcvault.com/play/1024913/Board-Game-Design-Day-Balancing>

- McCallum, S., & Boletsis, C. (2013). A Taxonomy of Serious Games for Dementia. In *Games for Health* (pp. 219–232). Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-02897-8_17
- Michael, D., & Chen, S. (2006). *Serious Games : Games That Educate, Train, and Inform*. Thomson Course Technology. Retrieved from <http://site.ebrary.com/lib/drexel/Doc?id=10087000&ppg=1>
- Newbury, E. M. H. (2017, November 30). Award-Winning Online Game Helps Voters Steer America’s ‘Fiscal Ship.’ Retrieved April 20, 2024, from <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/award-winning-online-game-helps-voters-steer-americas-fiscal-ship>
- Önal, U. (2023). *Generalized Game-Testing Using Reinforced Learning* (Master’s Thesis). Istanbul Technical University.
- Papastergiou, M. (2009). Exploring the potential of computer and video games for health and physical education: A literature review. *Computers and Education*, 53(3), 603–622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2009.04.001>
- Pendergrass, D., & Vettese, T. (n.d.). Half-Earth Socialism A Plan to Save the Future from Extinction, Climate Change and Pandemics. Retrieved from <https://www.half.earth/about>
- Pilon, M. (2015, April 11). The Secret History of Monopoly: The Capitalist Board Game’s Leftwing Origins. *The Guardian*.
- Portnow, J. (2012, August 2). Perfect Imbalance - Why Unbalanced Design Creates Balanced Play - Extra Credits. Retrieved December 17, 2023, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e31OSVZF77w>
- Rouse, R. (2001). *Game Design: Theory & Practice*. Wordware Pub.
- Rubin, S., & DeCoster, R. (2018). PAX South 2018 -- Balance in Game Design. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NXD8YQ7j_Qk

- Salen, K., & Zimmerman, E. (2003). *Rules of Play: Game Design Fundamentals*. The MIT Press.
- Schell, J. (2020). *Tenth Anniversary The Art of Game Design A Book of Lenses* (3rd ed.). Boca Raton: CRC press.
- Schreiber, I., & Romero, B. (2022). *Game Balance*. Boca Raton: CRC Press.
- Sheiner, L., Wessel, D., & Pita, A. (2016, May 11). Keeping the U.S. Fiscal Ship afloat. Retrieved April 20, 2024, from <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/keeping-the-u-s-fiscal-ship-afloat/>
- Sirlin, D. (2009). *Balancing Multiplayer Competitive Games Why Care About Balance?*
- Smith, A. M., Nelson, M. J., & Mateas, M. (2009). Computational Support for Play Testing Game Sketches. *Proceedings of the Fifth Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment Conference*, 167–172. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aiide.v5i1.12368>
- Street, G. (2017). Balancing “League of Legends” for Every Player, from Bronze to Bengi. Retrieved January 27, 2024, from Game Developers Conference website: <https://gdcvault.com/play/1024237/Balancing-League-of-Legends-for>
- Sylvester, T. (2013). *Designing Games: A Guide to Engineering Experiences*. O’Reilly Media.
- Thomas, R. J., Masthoff, J., & Oren, N. (2019). Can I Influence You? Development of a Scale to Measure Perceived Persuasiveness and Two Studies Showing the Use of the Scale. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2019.00024>
- Tseng, F., Pham, S. La, Pendergrass, D., & Vettese, T. (2022). Half-Earth Socialism (PC Version).
- Ute, R., Michael, C., & Peter, V. (2009). *Serious Games: Mechanisms and Effects* (U. Ritterfeld, M. Cody, & P. Vorderer, Eds.). Routledge, Taylor and Francis.

- Vettese, T., & Pendergrass, D. (2022). *Half-Earth Socialism: A Plan to Save the Future from Extinction, Climate Change and Pandemics* (1st ed.). Verso.
- Wang, W. (2023). *International Series on Computer, Entertainment and Media Technology: The Structure of Game Design* (N. Lee, Ed.). Springer.
- Wattanasoontorn, V., Boada, I., García, R., & Sbert, M. (2013). Serious games for health. *Entertainment Computing*, 4(4), 231–247.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.entcom.2013.09.002>
- Wessel, D. (2016a, April 26). Why we made a computer game about the federal budget. Retrieved April 20, 2024, from <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/why-we-made-a-computer-game-about-the-federal-budget/>
- Wessel, D. (2016b, April 27). How we picked the debt goal for The Fiscal Ship. Retrieved April 20, 2024, from <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/how-we-picked-the-debt-goal-for-the-fiscal-ship/#:~:text=To%20make%20the%20game%20playable,that%2075%25%20is%20too%20high.>
- Wessel, D. (2016c, July 18). How to Right the U.S. ‘Fiscal Ship.’ *The Wall Street Journal*. Retrieved from <https://www.wsj.com/articles/BL-WB-64427>
- Zackariasson, P., & Wilson, L. T. (2012). *The Video Game Industry: Formation, Present State, and Future*. New York: Routledge.